

INFLUENCE OF THE INSTITUTIONAL GOVERNANCE MODEL ON THE INTERNATIONALISATION OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN SOUTH AFRICA

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the institutional governance model based on public accountability, transparency, fairness, and integrity and its influence on South Africa's higher education internationalisation. Hence, the adoption of a systematic review approach to shape the scope for an all-inclusive, transparent discourse analysis and insightful discussion on related empirical studies. The sources at the centre of this discussion are selected through set inclusion and exclusion criteria. This systematic literature review was conducted grounded in a theoretical framework comprised of stakeholder, neo-institutional, and de-colonial theories. It was noted that the interaction between tenets of the institutional governance model contributes to the creation of a firm foundation for South Africa's higher education internationalisation. This is anchored on the interface between quality management and higher education corporatisation in the context of academic freedom and institutional autonomy. Despite these implications, some challenges are met when grounding the institutional governance model in the matrix of higher education internationalisation in South Africa. From this, it has been concluded that the interaction between public accountability, transparency, fairness, and integrity forges a network capable of enhancing quality management and corporatization in South Africa's higher education. Hence, the institutional governance model has the potential to influence South Africa's higher education internationalisation positively. Therefore, it is recommended that South Africa adopt a multi-dimensional approach to resolving challenges formed by cultural multiplicity in the internationalisation of higher education.

Keywords: higher education, institutional governance model, internationalisation, South Africa

INTRODUCTION

The attainment of independence by South Africa in 1994 has ushered in transformations to the higher education environment (De & Altbach, 2021). This has been made possible through the exchange of ideas, knowledge and practices between nations (i.e., developed – developing or developed – developed) (Alexiadou & Rönnerberg, 2023). This has been made possible through a greater awareness of information, opportunities, and an increased propensity for higher education institutions to interact with those in Southern Africa and beyond (Ge, 2022). Therefore, the internationalisation of higher education facilitated the movement (i.e., virtual or real) of students, scholars, and professional development programmes from South Africa to other countries or vice versa. Thus, higher education was not restricted to either state or regional cultural boundaries (Thondhlana et al., 2021). This has been shaped by the emergence of technologies and ever-changing economies, and these forces are outside the mere control of higher education institutions (Waghid, 2023). This has intensified interconnectedness and expectations of higher education to drive competition between institutions within South Africa and beyond (Hazelkorn, 2018). This changing environment within higher education has brought governance issues to the fore in reshaping the roles and institutional structures (Maringe & Foskett, 2010).

In this regard, various scholars (Agnew & Van, 2009; Buckner, 2019; Burnett & Huisam, 2010; Josava & Roxå, 2019; Johnstone & Proctor, 2018) postulated the role of the institutional governance model in mediating higher education's position towards internationalisation. These institutions were expected to take higher education as a business. Thus, corporations were seen as the platform to enhance the internationalisation of higher education. However, concerns have been raised pertaining to the influence of the institutional governance model on higher education internationalisation in South Africa. Hence, this paper sought to gain insight into pertinent issues for desirable institutional governance and its influence on internationalisation. In this regard, it questions the interplay between the institutional governance model and higher education internationalisation in South Africa. The interrogation was guided by the following key question: How does the institutional governance model influence the internationalisation of higher education in South Africa?

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

In South Africa, higher education internationalisation is considered a transformation process in line with the protocol on education and training, which integrates various systems through cooperation and collaboration (Maringe, et al., 2013). It is against this background that this paper embraced a theoretical framework comprised of stakeholder, neo-institutional, and de-colonialisation theories in a bid to attain an all-inclusive comprehension of the issue under discussion. The stakeholder theory advocates for the provision of balance between the interests of students, academics, government, industry, etc., in higher education institutions' operations to meet their satisfaction (Yusoff & Idris, 2012). In addition, the neo-institutional theory postulates that higher education institutions' operations and behaviour are guided by policies, programmes, practices, and shared norms, which accord their legitimacy (Thondhlana et al., 2021). Thus, such forces the internationalisation process of these institutions by offering them the opportunity to transform consciously by local needs and environment (Ndaipa, et al., 2023).

Consequently, South Africa adopted ideas and practices geared towards decolonisation. This is so since the higher education internationalisation agenda in numerous African nations still bears traces of colonialism (Mbembe, 2016). Hence, the agenda of internationalisation of higher

education needs to consider issues to do with globalisation, de-imperialisation, and de-colonisation (Ndlovu, 2018). This makes it imperative that this paper adopt the de-colonisation theory, with the view to opposing the prevailing Eurocentric epistemic canon and privileging the conception of mutuality among communities the world over (Santos, 2018). This framework formed the lens through which governing practices (internal systems and structures) were explored in a bid to determine their role in encouraging the existence of transparency, accountability, fairness and integrity for higher education institution's competitive edge in internationalisation. Hence, in this paper, internationalization was introduced with the motive of making higher education institutions become world-class based on power relations and in conformity to the atmosphere of commonality, equity, and justice.

In this context, effective higher education is partly anchored on governance structures and principles (Bingab et al., 2018). These include well-articulated regulations, and quality assurance controls responsive to the demands of the stakeholders (Vries, 2013). In this case, institutional governance needs to integrate issues like leadership, funds, infrastructure and competitiveness in a bid to provide quality service locally and internationally (Forson & Opoku, 2014). This calls for the existence of the process of exchange and governance between the higher education institution and its stakeholders (i.e., government through the responsible ministry, students, academics, industry, etc.).

METHODOLOGY

In this conceptual paper, a systematic review approach was used to locate relevant literature sources concerning South Africa's higher education internationalisation. Hence, a literature review was the primary tool that was used to explore the research gap in the context of the issue under investigation. In this regard, the review centred on key bibliographic databases: DHTE, DOAJ, EBSCOhost, Google Scholar, Elsevier, and Web of Science. Specifically, the search targeted 'institutional governance culture*' OR 'governance culture*' OR 'internationalisation*' OR 'higher education*' AND 'internationalisation of higher education*' OR 'corporatisation of higher education*' OR 'South Africa*' used in titles, abstracts, keywords, and references. The targeted sources were purposively included in this paper based on their titles and their relevance to the issues raised. If the material appeared to deliberate the issue at the centre of this conceptual paper, its full reference was obtained for further assessment. Below is a pictorial representation of the sources' selection procedure.

Figure 1: Relevant Sources Selection Procedure

Refer to Figure 1; the search on the above databases focused on articles issued between 2000 - 2024. Thus, 95 potential sources, including 15 duplicates, were later excluded. The 80 potential sources were then screened for inclusion by considering the relevance of their abstracts to the issue under discussion. The researchers conducted parallel independent assessments of the potential sources. Full texts of the selected sources were obtained such their quality and eligibility can be assessed. This discussion only included those sources that were published by reputable editors that were deemed to be of considerable quality. In this case, 27 sources, through independent parallel assessment, were excluded because their content was irrelevant to the issue under discussion. Overall, 53 sources were considered relevant sources of information and included in the subsequent phase of content analysis. In these sources, relevant information was extracted, guided by the themes of this paper. The extracted data was analysed using discourse analysis to identify themes and within the theoretical lens guiding this paper. This was intended to explore the meaning behind the texts in different sources that were consulted in line with the issue under investigation.

FINDINGS

After selecting sources that were deemed relevant for this paper, they were interrogated according to the identified themes. In this regard, findings are analysed under the following themes:

INSTITUTIONAL GOVERNANCE MODEL AS A FOUNDATION FOR HIGHER EDUCATION CORPORATISATION

This section elaborates on how institutional governance culture creates the foundation for higher education internationalisation. In line with this idea, Section 31 of the Higher Education Act articulates in terms of the governance of higher education that institutions need an 'institutional forum' comprised of management representatives, council, academics, non-academics and students (Heleta, 2023). Thus, higher education institutions' governance model was anticipated to operate guided by all-encompassing market economic values (managerialism), in which rationalism and revenue ideals propel their operations (Adams, 2006). This calls for the democratisation of institutional governance structures (that is the councils or senates) (Altbach, 2015; Cloete & Kulati, 2003).

This is a paradigm shift to rationality that combines the economic, social, and political dimensions to provide quality education at low cost through the betterment of its systems' productivity and effectiveness (Abdulrahman et al., 2020). This is made possible with the existence of a viable rapport between the central government and institutions. Thus, the state through its centralised authority (the Minister of Higher Education) through the National Department of Education uses either planning and funding or assessment of outcomes to shape the university systems. Hence, this management style enabled the government to play its oversight obligation to guarantee some acceptable standards of public accountability.

So, the government watches the game between autonomous players (senate, councils, faculties, departments, students, industry, parents or guardians, etc.) and reviews the regulations or procedures as soon as the game tends to be against the expected outcomes (Hall & Symes, 2005). Thus, most of the decisions are made at the institutional level and the central authority (through the Department of Higher Education and Training) with a focus on monitoring standards and the framework for procedures guiding the behaviour of stakeholders (Mtotywa,

et al., 2024). This brings on board the notion that the government (through the Department of Higher Education and Training) plays a supervisory role with much respect to academic freedom as enshrined in the constitution.

The existence of such an arrangement assures the quality of academics and maintains an expected standard of public accountability in higher education institutions (Dodd, et al., 2023). This is purported to bring about mutual and shared commitment from all stakeholders involved in institutional governance issues. This calls for the relevance of consultations and dialogue between the state and the stakeholders involved in institutional governance activities (Varghese, 2013). This transformation has accorded higher education institutions the responsibility to manage their affairs (Scott, 2013). This implies institutional autonomy that is meant to prevail concurrently with public accountability. In this sense, higher education systems have their governance structures (e.g., councils), which operate in an environment influenced by a set of external procedures and systems (Omal, 2023; Cloete & Kulati, 2003). It is against this background that the next section articulates corporatisation and its influence on higher education internationalisation.

HIGHER EDUCATION CORPORATISATION WITHIN THE MEDIUM OF QUALITY MANAGEMENT, ACADEMIC FREEDOM AND INSTITUTIONAL AUTONOMY

The institutional governance in higher education can be linked to the affinity of globalisation supposing that education to be intellectualised and operationalised like other services or businesses (Rossouw & Goldman, 2023). So, higher education institutions can operate in an environment driven by economic rationalism and profit ideals (Cornelius & Bell, 2023). This thrust focuses on the delivery of quality higher education at a reasonable cost be it to local or international students (Wood, 2010). The operations of these institutions are guided by the criteria of performance created by bureaucratic agencies (such as the NQF and SAQA) (Adams, 2006; Ojo & Booth, 2009). These agencies put in place rules for reporting and public accountability necessary for assessment and the application of formulas linking assessed 'quality' and funding (Czerniewicz et al., 2023; Peters et al., 2000). This concurs with the ideals of managerialism in that it generates checks and balances within the higher education system.

It is in this context that many institutions operate under the guidance of managerialism to facilitate continued transformation in quality and efficiency (Habib, 2016). This creates a platform for constant assessment of externally accredited programmes and in turn, is linked to funding (Van & Havenga, 2023). This brings on board the economic dimension, which considers education as a commodity (that is bought like any other consumer product on the market). It is against this background that the state (through the Department of Higher Education and Training) and institutions put at the centre of their operations, efficiency, and an ethic of cost-benefit analysis in a bid to establish a link between the economy or market and higher education system (Apple, 2000).

This inevitably gives direction to the operations in the higher education system (Enslin et al., 2003) in a bid to internationalise their institutions. In this regard, higher education corporatisation exhibits that the authority to make decisions was in the custody of institutional administrative 'managers' (Saidi & Boti, 2023). This belief in the power of the corporative management approach in higher education institutions has necessitated their inclination towards entrepreneurial culture. In this case, business practices, ideas, and values have permeated higher education institution structures (Abugre, 2018). This has created institutional and faculty competition for funding from international grants, contracts, university-industry partnerships, etc. (Chipindi & Daka, 2022). This burgeoning managerialism has institutions setting targets and key

performance areas as a way of operationalizing the institutions (Rossouw & Goldman, 2023). This has been made possible by the need to enhance global competitiveness, internationalisation, quality education, global knowledge, and sustainable development (Anzola, 2020).

DISCUSSION

From the findings presented in the previous section, it was noted that the independent South Africa adopted a transformative agenda for its higher education institutions. This was centred around remodeling their structures, instructional practices, modes of academic governance, and managerial systems in line with the expectations of the 21st-century communities in South Africa and even beyond its borders. In this context, higher education institutions were looked upon as images of national pride, and this granted them the opportunity to receive support from the national fiscus. This called for the shift in institutional governance to internationalism their operations although the process was embroiled in some inextricable processes. For instance, there was a decline in financial support from the external funders and government which was subsidizing the higher education system. In this regard, the higher education institutions in the South transformed their internal systems (identities, academic faculties, departments, and management) with the view to match the external pressures. Thus, the transformation of leadership, governance, and management styles in South African higher education has been influenced by the movement of students, academics, courses, qualifications, etc., from one country to another (Council on Higher Education, 2022).

In this regard, higher education institutions experience their autonomy within a framework of leadership through planning or funding and in cooperation with the National Qualifications Framework and the South African Qualifications Authority as a way of ensuring public accountability. Therefore, the principle of shared governance is that key stakeholders (councils, academics, non-academics and students) within higher education participate in institutional decision-making. This brings on board authority based on expertise and capability much-needed in making informed decisions to drive the operations of the system. This calls for the need for the stakeholders to ground the institutional governance issues (that is, policy making, decision making, etc.) in trust, with the view to advance its vision, mission, and integrity and to keep in mind the importance of public accountability. Consequently, the interaction between public accountability, transparency, fairness, and integrity contributes to the corporatisation of higher education institutions.

In this case, no single group has the institutional power to overwhelm another group in the administrative control of the system. This is in harmony with the idea of decentralisation (thinning of the state's role) and advocacy for quality management of higher education institutions. So, this setup ensures institutional 'autonomy' where institutional forums (such as the senate or councils, etc.) play the advisory role to the operations in line with the intentions of the local or international market. However, there is an in-built governance machinery in these institutions to confine autonomy and enhance the implementation of government-related policies under the guise of public accountability and quality management.

The above ensures that institutions in South Africa are more entrepreneurial and commercially responsive to societal (i.e., national or international) demands with much efficiency (Davis et al., 2016). Hence, this new thrust in higher education is profit-driven and calls upon academics to enhance their career paths and their institution's market share. This transformation in institutional culture has impacted academics' professional identities. In this context, an array of bureaucratic processes has been put in place, such as results-based management systems,

targets, and performance procedures. This has led to a regime of accountability and the use of regulations to police academics through adherence to the goals, objectives, and instructions given by the management.

IMPLICATIONS OF THE FINDINGS

This paper was an attempt to bring about a better understanding of how an institutional governance model acts as a foundation for corporatization to enhance quality management, academic freedom and autonomy. In other words, this creates a platform for interaction between various stakeholders with the view to enhance the institution's image and competitiveness within and outside South Africa. In addition, the findings can contribute towards the creation of protocols to determine how higher education institutions can internationalise in accordance with all the stakeholders' interests. This, in a way, can foster ethical institutional governance practices, leading to the institution's viability both locally and beyond the borders.

AREA FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

While this qualitative approach was useful in gaining insight into the issue under interrogation, this phenomenon can be further examined using a quantitative approach. The quantitative approach can show mathematically the influence of accountability, transparency, fairness, and integrity on the internationalisation of higher education.

CONCLUSION

South Africa's higher education has been confronted with a need to transform due to globalisation and the knowledge revolution since the realization of independence. Hence, these institutions have no other alternative besides that of ensuring competitiveness in the world rankings. This call for sustainability and an astute character such that the institutions can be well-positioned demands quality and customer-centeredness. It is in this context that higher education institutions have adopted the internationalisation thrust to provide a forum that avails expertise and cooperation. This new thrust enabled higher education institutions in South Africa to find creative ways to transform such as re-looking their 'business models' in serving the socioeconomic agenda and to be institutions of 'public good' both nationally and internationally. It is against this background that this discussion concludes that the interaction between the tenets of the institutional governance model (that is, public accountability, transparency, fairness, and integrity) influences South Africa's higher education internationalisation.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There is no conflict of interest in this study.

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